

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference

Knowledge, Skills, and Innovation in
sustainable construction for a resilient future of Europe

Barcelona, February 27, 2026, 10:00-18:00

UNESCO-UIA Barcelona 2026 World Capital of Architecture

Co-hosted by the Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC),
InnovaWood, and the University of Primorska

- **Europe's economy** must transition towards a sustainable, digital, and inclusive future by enhancing **competitiveness** and **resilience**, delivering on **social needs** and **climate goals**.
- The **New European Bauhaus Academy** is the European Commission's **flagship initiative** for skills development, knowledge, experimentation, and innovation enabling the clean transition of the construction sector.
- The **1st NEB Academy Conference** will showcase good practices in skills development for sustainable construction and reflect on the Academy's future role as a support system to create more **beautiful**, **creative**, and **regenerative** built environments and neighbourhoods in Europe.

Join us to learn, network and engage with the NEB community!

Goals of the 1st NEB Academy Conference

The **NEB Academy's mission** is to support the European construction ecosystem to achieve carbon neutrality and a beautiful, sustainable, and inclusive transformation of the economy. In light of a new emerging global context, it will provide a full support system for practitioners: from knowledge development to capacity-building, experimentation, and replication/scale-up.

The NEB Academy is guided by the 2025 European Commission's **Communication on the New European Bauhaus**, and contributes to the EU ambition to move towards a climate neutral and circular economy, to the **Clean Industrial Deal**, the **EU Bioeconomy Strategy**, the **EU Water Resilience Strategy**, the **European Affordable Housing Plan**, the **European Strategy for Housing Construction**, and the **Circular Economy Act**. The ambition is to establish the NEB Academy as the European point of reference for knowledge, skills, and innovation in bio-based, circular, and digital solutions for the built environment.

- **Learn** about the NEB Academy Alliance's first achievements and the future of the Academy.
- **Network** with the Alliance, Hub partners and stakeholders. Up to 80 participants are expected.
- **Engage** in the codesign of the next phase of the NEBA community in Europe and beyond.

UNESCO World Capital of Architecture & Venue

Iaac Institute for advanced architecture of Catalonia

The UNESCO World Capital of Architecture programming in Barcelona is led by the **Mies Foundation** in collaboration with **UNESCO**. The 1st NEB Academy Conference, co-hosted by the **Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC)** as the local partner, kicks off the series of world capital events and exhibitions.

barcelona.cat/capitalmundialarquitectura/en

City Council of Barcelona's Culture and Education Centre

Former headquarters of the Gustavo Gili publishing company, a notable example of 1950's rationalist architecture by Jauquin Gili and Francesc Bassó, awarded the FAD Prize for architecture in 1961. Centrally located in Barcelona's Eixample district at Carrer de Rosselló 87-89
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1st NEB Academy Conference - Programme

Co-hosted by IAAC, InnovaWood, University of Primorska

Venue: Gustavo Gili building - City Council of Barcelona's Culture and Education Centre, Carrer de Rosselló 87-89 share.google/w2o40zlg2VRmeoMA5

09:30 – 10:00 Arrival and Registration of participants

10:00 – 10:30 **Welcome and opening speeches**

[Anna Ramos](#), Mies Foundation, Director

[Ruth Reichstein](#), European Commission,
Member of Cabinet of President Ursula von der Leyen

[Daniel Ibañez](#), IAAC, CEO/Director

10:30 – 11:00 **The NEBA Alliance: a European network of training hubs**

[Andreja Kutnar](#), University of Primorska, coordinator of the NEBA Alliance

11:00 – 12:15 **NEB Academy Hubs: first achievements and success stories** (6 short talks)

- **Train-the-trainers course for professionals in timber construction**
NEBAP Hub: [Martin Greimel](#), BOKU Centre for Bioeconomy, Austria
- **NEBA North Hub: Co-Creating the New European Bauhaus Across Estonia, Finland and Sweden** | [Camilla Berggren-Tarrodi](#), RISE, Sweden & [Sille Pihlak](#), EKA, Estonia
- **Teaching NEB to students of architecture**
NEBAP Hub: [Anetta Kepczynska-Walczak](#) & [Bartosz Walczak](#),
Łódź University of Technology, Poland
- **From forest to frame / Unlearning energy and material cultures**
Central Hub: [Elena Markus](#), Bauhaus Earth, Germany
- **Industrialized wood construction programme & prefab training school MaderAula**
South Hub: [Michael Salka](#), IAAC & [Manuel Garcia Barbero](#), Cesefor, Spain
- **NEB and Place-making in the NEB Sud Hub | LIFE BE-WoodEN**
[Giovanna Franco](#), University of Genoa & [Beatrice Zerega](#), Regione Liguria, Italy

12:15 – 12:45 Coffee break

- 12:45 – 13:00 **The future of the NEB Academy**
Elena Montani, European Commission JRC, Head of Unit - New European Bauhaus
- 13:00 – 14:00 **Panel: The role of skills and innovation in the future NEB Academy**
Matti Kuittinen, Aalto University – NEBA North Hub (moderator of panel)
Ambra Trotto, EIT Culture & Creativity, Director of RIS and Transformation
Selma Harrington, Union of International Architects & Architects' Council of Europe
Vicente Guallart, IAAC, Co-Founder – NEBA South Hub
Uwe Kies, InnovaWood, Secretary General – NEBA Outreach Hub
- 14:00 – 15:00 Lunch
- 15:00 – 15:45 **NEB Project Pitches** (PechaKucha, 6 talks of 7 min)
- **NEB Junction: Open NEB platforms for sharing knowledge**
Aksel Borgen, NTNU, Norway
 - **PulseArt: Cultural Awareness and Expression for Inclusion and Civic Participation**
Marine Masson, Science for Change, Spain
 - **NEB Academy Hub in Ukraine: Skills for Reconstruction**
Ksenia Semenova, Operations Director, Metalab, Ukraine
Yaryna Stepanyuk, Local development advisor, U-LEAD with Europe, GIZ
 - **Eyes Hearts Hands: The NEB Urban Revolution**
Carlo Battisti, Living Future Europe, Italy
 - **Bauhausing: Public buildings renovation**
Carlos Egio, EuroVértice Consultores, Spain
- 15:45 – 16:30 **Networking Session** (interactive meeting spots)
- 16:30 – 17:00 Coffee break
- 17:00 – 18:00 **Keynote by SUMA Arquitectura**, winners of the 2024 EUMies Award
Guillermo Sevillano Bengoechea, Spain
- 18:00 – 18:00 Closing words